

PANJAPATCHI

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Abstract:

Scientific basic of panchapakshi is five activities & their relevance as basic concept with regard to functioning of the world Eating, Walking, Ruling, Sleeping, Dying. Space of Ecliptic showing of Longitudes of the Moon of One's Birth – Birds sounds & Letters, Strength of different birds-Signification of day half period of moon cycle – Horary Elemental Astrology panchapakshi arooda through Stars.

Key Words: Peacock, Crow, Owl, Vulture, Eating, Walking, Ruling, Sleeping, Dying.

Introduction:

We live in an era in which people talk of biorhythms to be able to achieve the very best in the pursuit of their ambitions. What they have improved in the West is most elementary, most generalised and loose and more fanciful than useful. Your biorhythms for a particular day, for a particular time, for a particular activity is dependent solely and entirely on your Janma Nakshatra (Your birth star). Before I explain the special utility of the Panchapakshi theory as given by Prof. Pulippani, let me start with the experience of Sri M.N.Kedar in the early part of 1991 when he had gone to Madras to attend a meeting of the Indian Council of Astrological Sciences after having got his return train ticket booked for return journey from Madras to Delhi. Something went false somewhere and his name was not there on the reservation list at all. Mr. Kedar tried to contract the concerned railway officials but was not succeeding, Mr. Pulippani with whom Mr. Kedar was at the station, asked him, what was his janmanakshatra. The particular questions of Mr. Pulippani would have been (now that I have read the manuscript), I guess these:

First the determination to hold the first ever All India Astrological Conference of the Indian Council of Astrological Sciences in September 1991 in Delhi. Secondly, our decision to produce a Sovevinik on theist occasion, (which turned Souvenirs out to be so good). Thirdly, we had a very valuable article on Panchapakshi by Prof. Pulippani. Fourthly, we had a very illumination lecture by him during the conference. And finally, his decision to hand over the English manuscript of his book on Panchapakshi to M/s.Ranjan Publications, to make this knowledge available to astrologers outside Tamilnadu for the very first time.

Having given this introduction let me refer briefly to the features of the book.

- Pancha means five and Pakshi means birds. All human beings are categorised under fire birds - Vulture, OWL, Crow, Cock and Peacock. This is fixed and is based on your birth-star.
- Each bird, every day, is indulging into five activities - active (eating.), more active (walking) most active (rulling). Inactive (sleeping) and then a total point of cessation of all activities, (death).
- Each day is divided into five divisions of two hours and twenty four minutes (yamas) and similarly night is divided into such five equal divisions (yamas). Six ghaties (twenty four minutes for each ghaty) is one yama.
- Now since it is dependent on janmanakshatra you must find out if your birth is during the bright half of a month or a dark half of a month.
- Then again all months are not uniformly good for all. It is obvious and will appeal to anyone's commonsense those seasonal variations cause spurts of brilliant activities and spells of lassitude and inactivity.
- Similarly all days, Monday and Tuesday etc., cannot be good and same for all. The ruling planet of the day, Mars, may be good for one Pakshi but not favourable for another.
- Then there are holidays for each Pakshi. There must be a rest day for each Pakshi.
- Then the night activities must have different patterns.
- What about persons who do not know their janma Nakshatra? It is solved in two ways; Find out the prominent vowel in their names. Each vowel in turn gets identified with a bird. All vowels are categorised into five,
- Then there are five directions, East, West, North, South and centre. Again five.

Introduction of the Subject:

- The Scientific Basic of Panchapakshi. [Bio-Rhythms]

Every human being is after pursuit of happiness in the world. Nobody intentionally accepts sorrow and misery. As a matter of fact, life consists of more sorrow and grief than happiness. Right from the dawn of civilization, great thinkers and Saints were in the true pursuit to find out ways and means to get pure happiness, without any trace of sorrow whatsoever. After continued research and penance for centuries, they have to come to the conclusion that only spiritualism leading to self-realization is the way to enjoy and experience everlasting bliss. In this effort and path, ancient Tamil *Sidhas* stand in the fore front. They have formulated a "Golden Key" to un-lock the doors of the bosom of super intelligence and see face to face, this everlasting bliss.

These Sidhas were not only great spiritualists to the core, but also, great scientists, physicians and psychologists, who analysed life in the fullness both on Mundane and abstract levels and dictated scientific principles leading man to success of both levels. On the gross plane, if one lives in accordance with the nature, life becomes blessing which in the long run leads to spiritual well being also. In such a seeking, the mysterious Panchapakshi is one of the which helps man progress simultaneously on par, and, in accordance with the nature and both the planes and get enduring bliss.

In a nutshell, the following is the essence of this science as enunciated by ancient Siddha Saints. The soul, the body it dwells in, the feelings etc., are resultant of collective forms of the vibrations of five basic elements consisting in various proportions. When an individual's vibrations are repelling with those in Macrocosm, suffering begins. Conversely, when the elemental vibration of an- Individualism is in tune with those in Macrocosm, the individual gets satisfaction and happiness.

In the former conditions, there will always be failures and sufferings and in the latter, there will always be success and comforts, similarly, when the individual tunes up his elemental vibrations in the abstract plane with those of the super intelligence, he gets emancipation in the spiritual field. This is the basis of **Panchapakshi:**

These great Tamil yogis found out that the Planetary movements, the waxing and the waning periods of the moon due to its relative cyclic distance from the sun and due to the radiation of these Planets Progressing through the ecliptic consisting of 12 apartments called SINGS and 27 HINDU constellations evenly spread over these signs, produce a specialised elemental vibrative force at each of the time situations.

They also found that these elemental vibrations differently function in 5 ways during the periods of waxing and waning Moon cycles in 5 differentially function in 5 different gradations. When a human is ushered into this world, the cosmic vibrations, emanations from the peculiar pattern of the NINE Planets by virtue of occupation of their particular and angular position in the ecliptic give a collective imprint in the sub-conscious. They are combined with the elemental vibrations occurring in the path of the compartments of the 27

constellations in the ecliptic. The Jataga can thus be defined as a symbolic representation of this imprint. Being controlled/ directed by this mark, the individual is helpless, but to live in a peculiar individual way accordingly. If we can identify the fundamental laws behind formation of this imprint and the functional pattern of our elemental vibrations, we can adjust ourselves and function in such a way so that people indulge in any action during a time-situation whenever elemental vibrations are at the highest ebb we will be crowned with supreme success. This is the fundamental of this

Panchaprakshi:

- How the Panchapakshi Function?

These 5 elemental vibrations act in 5 gradations of faculties for stipulated time intervals called (YAMAS) consisting of 2hrs. 24 mins, each (6 Ghatikas each) over the 5 YAMAS in the day and 5 YAMAS in the night, thus spread over evenly in 24 hours. These functional patterns vary, during waxing and waning Moon cycles, and also during the week days. These elemental vibrations of 5 gradations function in such a way that when one elemental vibration is at the highest ebb, the other four function proportionately in diminishing order, thus the last vibration is a dormant or a "death". These 5 elemental vibrations are personified as PAKSHIS or BIRDS and the gradations of their faculties are named as 5 activities. The 5 birds are named as follows:

- Vulture
- Owl
- Crow
- Cock
- Peacock

These 5 Activities of the Birds are Named as Follows:

- Eating
- Walking
- Ruling
- Sleeping
- Dying

Each bird performs these five activities during each day and in the night over the week days and during waxing and waning Moon cycles during the 5 YAMAS in day and 5 YAMAS in night in a stipulated order which are explained in the text in the proper context.

The Five Activities and Their Relevance as Basic Concept with Regard to Functioning of the World:

Basically, the concept of life on earth consists of these 5 activities only viz., Eating, Walking, Ruling, Sleeping and Dying. All animate things, in the world, do these 5 activities regularly without any exception in the process towards the progress of life.

- Eating: This activity is nothing but renewal of body cells, and thereby renewal of functional energy is thus effected.
- Walking: To eat, bread has to be earned. For earnings, movement is necessary. This movement is the Walking activity.
- Ruling: The process of earning itself is the activity of Ruling.
- Sleeping: After eating, walking and ruling, the system gets exhausted due to prolonged exertions resulting in the need to relax. This relaxing process is the sleeping activity.
- Dying: By repeating process of these four activities frequently, the body in which the soul resides, completely degenerates and reaches an extreme point when functioning of these four activities is no more possible. At this stage, the soul departs from the old body to take and enter into another new suitable body by way of reincarnation. This is called the activity of dying and the cycle again begins.

The ancients have also found out that these 5 activities including dying occur daily throughout our life in gross and subtle forms. Actually, this is the true philosophy of life which forms the basis of PANCHAPAKSHI. From this it can be seen that a fundamental basic truth of life is enunciated by our great ancients for application in our day to day life. We cannot but remain wondering at the scientific observational keenness of our ancients who were actually real scientists of life, in formulating and discovering this great truth of PANCHAPAKSHI.

It is to be noted that the activities of Dying, Sleeping, Walking, Eating and Ruling are stronger than the previous ones in the order given. Thus, the Dying and Sleeping states are very weak and unsuitable for any action, the Walking state is stronger, being of medium strength. The next stronger is the Eating state and stronger still and most powerful is the Ruling state. Thus, the Eating and Ruling activity periods will be suitable for all the actions of day to day life to consummate into success.

How the Elemental Bird is Decided?

This is done in two ways:-

- **Birth Ascendant:** According to birth time of an individual, the bird and its activity are decided just as ascendant is decided in the case of computing horoscope in astrology. This will be the individual's birth

bird. This is helpful only in determining the trend and nature of one's life, as is analysed in the case of horoscope from the rising sign and other features. The example with regard to calculating ones birth bird has to be worked out separately. As this aspect dose not form the subject matter of this book, the same will be brought out in a subsequent volume.

- **Birth Star:** According to birth constellation (Hindu star) and as per the phase of either waxing or waning Moon cycles, the bird is decided. Thus first of 5or 6 stars beginning from Aswini, are allocated and distributed among the 5 birds in a stipulated way. When once the five bird of an individual is decided according to his birth star, either in waxing or waning phase of Moon, the same will be his permanent stellar bird for both the phases of the Moon cycle. Only this five bird is taken into consideration for all practical purposes in day to day life. It is this view, which forms the subject matter of this book.

Yama works out to 2 hrs. 24mts. of our modern time. Thus, the distribution of 5 yamas will be as follows during day and night:

- First Yama - 6 A.M. to 8.24 A.M.
- Second Yama - 8.24 A.M. to 10.48 A.M.
- Third Yama - 10.48 A.M. to 1.12 P.M.
- Fourth Yama - 1.12 P.M. to 3.36 P.M.
- Fifth Yama - 3.36 P.M. to 6 P.M.

The Cycle repeats similarly for the night. It should be important that the modern time cycle at its lower division also follows sexagenary time cycle, since the hour consists of 60 minutes and a minute consists of one minute which explains the reason behind following this sexagenary time cycle by our ancients. It is to be important that the beginning of the day is reckoned from Sun rise to Sun set in Hindu system. Similarly night is reckoned from Sun set to set in Sun rise on the following day, thus consisting of 24 hours for one day. Taking standard Sun rise as 6 A.M., the placement of time gaps or yamas are variable to the extent of difference that occurs latter or earlier to 6 A.M. due to difference in Sun rise or Sun set.

Panchapakshi and Occult Powers:

It is well known that mental powers can be channalised and used in positive or negative ways for specific purposes by Occultists. The Former being called White Magic respectively. Our ancients have formulated ways and means to employ both White and Black Magic in the field or Panchapakshi to yield definite results both on constructive and destructive ways. However, our ancients have always warned that Magic should never be employed for destructive purpose unless it happens spontaneously due to the destiny of the other being. The Panchapakshi occultism comprises of conjuring of various forces when the elemental vibration of the bird of an individual is at the highest aimed at persons whose elemental vibrations are a lower level. They have also formulated ways and means to employ these vibration.

Fundamentals Explained:

As has been explained in the Introduction, man is born under the influence of one of the 5 elements which is personified as his stellar birth bird in the Elemental astrology of Tamils. This bird is called his birth Stello Lunar Bird. The birth of each individual is decided in two ways. One, according to the ascendant as in Astrology, and the other, is decided based on the birth star or the constellation of the individual. For the present, the former is not taken up now. Only the latter is explained which suits all practical purposes for applying the same in day to day life.

In Hindu Astrology, 27 Stars are considered mainly which spread over the twelve signs of the Zodiac, occupying a space of 13° 20' for each star and thus the 27 Stars are evenly distributed over the 12 signs rate of 2¼ stars in each sign. The Zodiac at the Birth star is the constellation occupied by the Moon during birth time. The Moon traverses the space of each star roughly in one day (13° 20' space) : Each of these 27 stars goes under a Hindu name and each day is ruled by a star thus traversed by the planet Moon. These periods are generally given in Indian Almanacs,

By referring to the ephemeris, one can find the longitude of the Moon at birth and thus locate the birth star according to the Table No.1, Once the birth star is known, the birth bird can easily be located.

Table 1: The 27 Stars and their Pakshis or Birds on the Ecliptic

S.No	Name of the Star (Hindu)	Identified by Colebrooke with	Space on Ecliptic	Birds of Star	
				Bright Half	Dark Half
1	Aswini	Alpha Arieties	0d-0'-13d-20'	Vulture	Peacock
2	Barani	Musca	13d-21'-26d-40'	Vulture	Peacock
3	Krithika	Pi Tauri	26d-41'-40d-00'	Vulture	Peacock
4	Rohini	Alpha Tauri	40d-01'-53d-20'	Vulture	Peacock
5	Mriga-Srisha	Lambda or Ionis	53d-21'-66d-40'	Vulture	Peacock
6	Aridra	Alpha or Ionis	66d-41'-80d-00'	Owl	Cock

7	Punarvasu	Beta-Geminorem	80d-01'-93d-20'	Owl	Cock
8	Pushya	Delta Caneri	93d-21'-106d-40'	Owl	Cock
9	Aslesha	Alpha 1 & 2	106d-41'-120d-00'	Owl	Cock
10	Makha	Alpha Leonis	120d-01'-123d-20'	Owl	Cock
11	Purva Phalguni	Delta Leonis	123d-21'-146d-40'	Owl	Cock
12	Uthara Phalguni	Beta Leonis	146d-41'-160d-00'	Crow	Crow
13	Hastha	Game or Delta corvi	160d-01'-173d-20'	Crow	Crow
14	Chitra	Alpha Virgins	173d-21'-186d-40'	Crow	Crow
15	Swathi	Alpas Boots	186d-41'-200d-00'	Crow	Crow
16	Vishakha	Alpha or Chi Librx	200d-01'-213d-20'	Crow	Crow
17	Anuradha	Delta Scorpionis	213d-21'-226d-40'	Cock	Owl
18	Jyesta	Alpha scorpionis	226d-41'-240d-00'	Cock	Owl
19	Moola	Lambda scorpionis	240d-01'-253d-20'	Cock	Owl
20	Purva-Shada	Delta sagittari	253d-21'-266d-40'	Cock	Owl
21	Utharashada	Tansagittari	266d-41'-280d-00'	Cock	Owl
22	Sravana	Alpha-Aquilx	280d-00'-293d-20'	Cock	Owl
23	Dhanistha	Alpha - Delphini	293d-21'-306d-40'	Cock	Owl
24	Sata-bisha	Lambda Aquirrii	306d-41'-320d-00'	Cock	Owl
25	Purvabhadra	Alpha - Pegasi	320d-01'-333d-20'	Cock	Owl
26	Utharabhadra	Alpha - Andrinex	333d-21'-346d-40'	Cock	Owl
27	Revathi	Zeta - Piscium	346d-41'-360-00'	Cock	Owl

Readers should always bear in mind that the Moon's longitude of one's birth should be arrived at in the sidereal Zodiac or the fixed Zodiac of the Hindu Astrology which is called Nirayana Moon's position at birth, by deducting the precision of equinoxes or the Ayanamsa as it is called, for the particular time of birth from the Tropical Zodiac longitude of the Moon or the Sayana longitude as it is called. Since Lahiri Ayanamsa is university accepted and adopted in India, the same is given separately in Table No.2 for the period from 1900 to 2000 A.D. Now we will work out some examples suppose Mr. Omprakash wants to find his birth stellar bird, his birth year being 1968 and the longitude of the Moon at his birth was 230° 42'. Now we have to deduct the Ayanamsa, the precision of equinoxes for his birth year from his tropical position of the Moon first.

Table 3: Space of Ecliptic showing the Longitudes of the Moon of One's Birth for Five Birds

Birds for Those Born During Bright Half of the Moon Cycle	Space in Ecliptic from 0degree to 360degree		Birds for Those Born During Dark Half of the Moon Cycle
Vulture	0 Deg	66Deg 40'	Peacock
Owl	66 Deg 41'	146 Deg 40'	Cock
Crow	146 Deg 41'	213 Deg 20'	Crow
Cock	213 Deg 21'	280 Deg 00'	Owl
Peacock	280 Deg 01'	360 Deg 00'	Vulture

Referring to Table No.2, Lahiri, gives 23°- 24'- 36" for the year 1968 as Ayanamsa. Now by deducting this from 230°-42' () 230-24' -36" 207-17 24". Hence this 207°-7'- 24" is the longitude of the Moon at his birth in the fixed or Nirayana Zodiac. Now, referring to Table No. 1, we find that this falls within the range of 200°-01 to 2130-20' which the space of stars Vishakha is. Hence, his birth stars. Is Vishakha, for which the bird is crow. Strangely enough for the stars from Uthara Phalguni to Vishakha viz., from 146°-41' to 213°-20' in the fixed Zodiac, the bird is the same for both the waxing and waning periods of the Moon viz.,

Bright Half or Dark Half:

Suppose, if Omprakash's longitude of the Moon at birth in the Tropical Zodiac is 267°-32', we have to find his birth bird, the situation will be different. First of all, we have to deduct the precision of equinoxes viz., Ayanamsa for the year 1968 from the longitude of the Moon at birth, thus 2670-32 () 23-24-36** 44-07-2". By watching at the table again, you find that this falls under the star Moola which extends from 240°-01' to 253-20'. Hence his stellar bird, if he was born during bright half period of Moon it will be Cock and if he was born during dark half period of Moon it will be Owl, Thus, his permanent stellar birth will be the same for both the periods for all practical purposes. Similarly, his constant stellar birth bird will be Owl in case his birth is during dark half and it will be the purposes. Similarly, other cases can also be done. (Refer to the table).

Others' Bird:

Now, we can apply this, for various purposes during various conditions in our day to day life. By this way, we have to identify the stello lunar birth bird of others also, whom we are dealing with or with whom we have to combat, complete or reconcile with, as the case may be. But it is almost always not possible to know the births data of such other individuals. For this purposes, our ancients have evolved a method of identifying the birth bird of other individuals by recognizing the first vowel sound that shoots out while uttering the name of such individual. Table No.4 gives this system. Here, we have to be very careful in identifying the first vowel

sound (and not the first vowel letter) of the other man's name. In this system, the vowels referred to are of the Dravidian Origin TAMIL and do not indicate the English vowel sounds. This should always be borne in mind. For this purpose, I have given the parallel sound letters in the Indian Devanagari script also (along with English) which are also common for Hindi which is universally know to some extent. (when birth star is not known),

Explanation:

In this table you will find in the middle column the vowels are repeated. This shows the short and long sound of these vowels in the Dravidian language which is peculiar to itself. It can be understood that the 11 vowels of the Dravidian Tamil language are distributed among the 5 birds. These vowels and consonants formed by them are to be identified from the first letter of the name of a person to locate his bird.

Table 4: Identification of Birds from first Sound of the first Letter of the Name of the Person

Bird in Bright Half of the Moon	First Vowel Pertaining to the first sound of the Name	Birds in Dark Half of the Moon
Vulture	A, AA, I, OW	peacock
Owl	E, EE	Vulture
Crow	VU, VUU	Owl
Cock	EA, EAA	Peacock
Peacock	O, OO	Crow

- It is to be noted that any person is born under the influence of any one of these activities of his birth stellar bird. By bird we mean, the elemental vibrations personified as the five birds, Vulture, Cock, Crow, Owl, and Peacock.
- Each of these five birds perform the above activities in succession in a stipulated order different from each other at the same time. In other words, no two birds perform the same activity at the same time gap. The order of priorities of these activities is different during week days, day, night etc. also during the two cycles of the Moon.
- When one bird is performing one activity, the remaining four birds will be performing the other four activities which differ from each other.
- Activities are stronger in the order given :
 - Dying
 - Sleeping
 - Walking
 - Eating
 - Ruling
- Eating and Ruling are higher in gradation and Ruling being the strongest of all.
- A Bird of higher activity wins over a bird of lower activity instantly. In this way, the Ruling activity wins over the remaining four activities viz., Eating, Walking, Sleeping and Dying

The eating activity gets defeated by Ruling activity but wins over the remaining three viz., Walking, Sleeping and Dying. The Walking activity gets defeated by Ruling and Eating activity but wins over the other two activities viz., Sleeping and dying. The Sleeping activity gets defeated by Ruling, Eating and Walking activities but wins over the Dying activity. The Dying activity gets defeated by all the other four activities and wins over none. These timings for days are:

- Eating 30 Mts
- Walking 36 Mts
- Ruling 48 Mts
- Sleeping 18 Mts
- Dying 12 Mts
- 2 Hrs.24 Mts

Strength of Different Birds:

The ancients have also given the strength of different birds as follows: During bright half period of Moon: 1. Crow- Full Strength. 2. Vulture 0.75 strength. 3. Owl 0.50 strength. 4. Cock - 0.25 strength. 5. Peacock 0.125 strength. Now the vibrational strength of abstract activities given in the table that are followed get further modified according to fractional factors given above which can be worked out as follows:

1. If we consider that the ruling activity is the strongest, the strength of the remaining activities of all birds will get reduced by 1/5 at each stage as follows. In ruling it will be 1.00, in eating, it will be 4/5, in walking it will be 3/5, in sleeping it will be 2/5, and at the last dormant dying stage it will be 1/5. This is common as far as the gradational strength of these activities are concerned.

Now, this strength, will get further reduced at the rate of the fractional factors given in the beginning regarding the natural strength of the five birds viz., Crow -1, Vulture - 0.75 etc. Here, you have to take it for granted that the strength of the activities of the birds will thus get reduced by 25% for Vulture, by 50% for Owl,

by 75% for Cock and by 87.5% at the last stage for Peacock. The Crow will have its full strength in all stages. They are computed and given in Table.No.5,

Table 5: Table Showing the Strength of Abstract Activities for the 5 Birds

Bird	Main Activity	Abstract Activities				
		Ruling	Eating	Walking	Sleeping	Dying
Crow Full Strength	Ruling	1.00	0.80	0.60	0.40	0.20
	Eating	0.80	0.64	0.48	0.32	0.16
	Walking	0.60	0.48	0.36	0.24	0.12
	Sleeping	0.40	0.32	0.24	0.16	0.08
	Dying	0.20	0.16	0.12	0.08	0.04
Vulture 75% Strength	Ruling	0.75	0.60	0.45	0.30	0.15
	Eating	0.60	0.48	0.36	0.24	0.12
	Walking	0.45	0.36	0.27	0.180	0.09
	Sleeping	0.30	0.24	0.180	0.120	0.06
	Dying	0.15	0.12	0.09	0.06	0.03
Owl 50% Strength	Ruling	0.50	0.40	0.30	0.20	0.10
	Eating	0.40	0.32	0.24	0.16	0.08
	Walking	0.30	0.24	0.18	0.12	0.06
	Sleeping	0.20	0.16	0.12	0.08	0.04
	Dying	0.10	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.02
Cock 25% Strength	Ruling	0.250	0.20	0.15	0.10	0.05
	Eating	0.20	0.16	0.12	0.08	0.04
	Walking	0.15	0.12	0.09	0.06	0.03
	Sleeping	0.10	0.08	0.6	0.04	0.02
	Dying	0.05	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.01
Peacock 12.5% Strength	Ruling	0.125	0.10	0.075	0.05	0.025
	Eating	0.10	0.08	0.06	0.04	0.02
	Walking	0.075	0.06	0.045	0.03	0.015
	Sleeping	0.050	0.04	0.03	0.02	0.010
	Dying	0.025	0.02	0.015	0.01	0.005

Significations for Day Half Period of Moon Cycle:

Order of sequence of main activities of the five birds during dark half period of Moon cycle for day time and for the week days.

One: During Sundays and Tuesdays (Day Time)

- During the first main period (Yama), the Cock Eats, the Owl Dies, the Peacock Sleeps, the Crow Rules and the Vulture Walks. During the second main Period (Yama), the Vulture Eats, the Cock Dies, the Owl Sleeps, the Peacock Rules and the Crow Walks.
- During the third Main period (Yama), the Peacock Eats food, the Crow Dies, the Vulture Sleeps, the Cock Rules and the Owl Walks.
- During the fourth main period (Yama), the Peacock Eats food, the Crow Dies, the Vulture Sleeps, the Cock Rules and the Owl Walks. During the Fifth main period (Yama), the Owl Eats, the Peacock Dies.
- The Crow Sleeps, the Vulture Rules and the Cock Walks.

Two: During Mondays and Saturdays (Day)

- During the first main period (Yama), the Peacock Eats, the Crow Dies, the Vulture Sleeps, the Cock Rules and the Owl Walks.
- During the second main Period (Yama), the Owl Eats, the Peacock Dies, the Crow Sleeps, the Vulture Rules and the Cock Walks.
- During the third Main period (Yama), the Cock Eats, the Owl Dies, the Peacock Sleeps, the Crow Rules and the Vulture Walks.
- During the fourth main period (Yama), the Vulture Eats, the Cock Dies, the Owl Sleeps, the Peacock Rules and the Crow Walks.
- During the Fifth main period (Yama), the Crow Eats, the Vulture Dies, the Cock Sleeps, the Owl Rules and the Peacock Walks.

Three: During Wednesdays (Day)

- During the first main period (Yama), the Crow Eats, the Vulture Dies the Cock Sleeps, the Owl Rules and the Peacock Walks
- During the second main Period (Yama), the Peacock Eats, the Crow Dies, the Vulture Sleeps, the Cock Rules and the Owl Walks.

- During the third Main period (Yama), the Owl Eats, the Peacock Dies, the Crow Sleeps, the Vulture Rules and the Cock Walks.
- During the fourth main period (Yama), the Cock Eats, the Owl Dies, the Peacock Sleeps, the Crow Rules and the Vulture Walks.
- During the Fifth main period (Yama), the Vulture Eats, the Cock Dies, the Owl Sleeps, the Peacock Rules and the Crow Walks.

Four: During Thursdays (Day)

- During the first main period (Yama), the Owl Eats, the Peacock Dies, the Crow Sleeps, the Vulture Rules and the Cock Walks.
- During the second main Period (Yama), the Cock Eats, the Owl Dies, the Peacock Sleeps, the Crow Rules and the Vulture Walks.
- During the third Main period (Yama), the Vulture Eats, the Cock Dies, the Owl Sleeps, the Peacock Rules and the Crow Walks.
- During the fourth main period (Yama), the Crow Eats, the Vulture Dies, the Cock Sleeps, the Owl Rules and the Peacock Walks.
- During the Fifth main period (Yama), the Peacock Eats, the Crow Dies, the Vulture Sleeps, the Cock Rules and the Owl Walks.

Five: During Fridays (Day)

- During the first main period (Yama), the Vulture Eats, the Cock Dies, the Owl Sleeps, the Peacock Rules and the Crow Walks.
- During the second main Period (Yama), the Crow Eats, the Vulture Dies, the Cock Sleeps, the Owl Rules and the Peacock Walks.
- During the third Main period (Yama), the Peacock Eats, the Crow Dies, the Vulture Sleeps, the Cock Rules and the Owl Walks.
- During the fourth main period (Yama), the Owl Eats, the Peacock Dies, the Crow Sleeps, the Vulture Rules and the Cock Walks.
- During the Fifth main period (Yama), the Cock Eats, the Owl Dies, the Peacock Sleeps, the Crow Rules and the Vulture Walks.

Conclusions:

Now, we have come to the concluding state of this volume. Other subjects of this Elemental Astrology include natal, Horary, Electional Astrology, Occult Practice, Sexual science, Spiritual science etc. If God willing, they may also follow in separate hand-outs.

Summary of Points to Remember:

- Elemental Astrology is used with the advantage when one's vibrational power of activities performed by his stellar/Lunar bird is at the highest, ebb, he can tackle all others, in matters what so ever, since all others will be with their vibrational force of elemental activities of their own birds in definitely at a lower level. Hence, he can succeed or win love or tide over all the situations in life by applying this vibrational force in a clever and intelligent manner. For example, if he wants to see his fiance love-making and get her consent for marriage! he can select a time gap when his bird is in the abstract activity of Ruling in the main activity of Ruling in the main activity of Ruling, especially on a Ruling Day of his bird, at the same time, when the bird of his finance or girl friend is in dying or sleeping abstract activity especially so in sleeping or dying or main activity especially so in sleeping or dying or main activity, more so, in its immune days, if he then goes to court her friendship and get her to his term, the love gets unfailingly successful.
- Suppose, if one wants, even if married, if his wife is some-what unaccommodative and does not willingly gives herself to him, for his gratification, if he selects a high virbational time gap similar to one explained above, she will give everything of herself at his disposal and heaven's enjoyment will be his. The same thing applies to a woman approaching her better-half also.

Horary Elemental Astrology Panchapakshi Arooda through Stars Prelude:

In the last chapter answering questions based on conditions and circumstances of various categories were explained where the answer was based on more than many significations. Here in this chapter answering questions based on the star ruling on that particular day (Nakshatra) in explained. We shall identify the star from the position of the Moon in the foxed zodic which will be one of the 27 stars vide chapter on Fundamentals; the bird pertaining to that particular star is then identified. Thereafter, the answers can be declared in accordance with the nature of the activity of that bird performed during that particular time of questioning. Naturally, if the activity being eating food and ruling, the answer will be affirmative, in case of the activity being walking the answer will be neither positive nor negative, in case of the balance two activities of sleeping and dying, the answer will be completely negative. Now the delineations of all the 27 stars are explained below. It should be noted that the birds will be different for bright half and dark half of period of the Moon.

At the above last condition, their will be income, Auspicious occasions will come to pass. Those who went out for journey will come back in groups also getting married. All will live with their kith and kin joyfully. The questioner will get much money. He will have male children. His relatives will improve and he will live with them with all satisfaction. The material thought of will come to his hand. All these things will come to pass within 18 days.

References:

1. Analytical Approach by Ashish Gujral Sagar Publications
2. The Nakshatras Panja Pakshi by J. M. Mehta V&S Publishers